

Analysis of Connectivity Matrix of Dindori Tahsil (Nashik District, Maharashtra)

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Introduction-

Connectivity of any nation determines the status of development of any nation. Developed, developing and undeveloped countries have different stages of connectivity. Most of developed parts of the world have indicator of good connectivity and have economic welfare. Connectivity directly determine by physical, environmental and economic factor. India is diversified in physical and environmental conditions. So there is varied range of transport network. State of Maharashtra have different type of physical setting. So, there is also variation in transport network. Dindori tahsil lies in Nashik district is located in northern part of District and have differences in physical and environmental settings. So Dindori tahsil is purposively selected to analyse connectivity matrix.

Methodology-

For the analysis of road transport network in Dindori Tahsil, only 20 settlements have been selected. These settlements have more than 5000 population in the Tahsil. The Topological graph is drawn for all the nodes and edges which are considered in the present analysis. Since the edges are not crossed or intersected except at the vertices, the graphs are treated as lanner graph. The road network which is considered for the network analysis, includes national high ways, state high ways, district roads and mandal roads. The network analysis is made for different periods of time namely 1980 and 2019 in order for the study of structural changes and development of road network.

Graph theory has been applied to calculate Alpha, Beta, Gama, Eta Index. The places located on the road which are all important centers and settlements having more than 3,000 population are considered as vertices and the transportation routes are considered as edges (Map No. 1 and 2). The conversion of network into graphic involves the application of topological properties. The enclosed topological graph consists of sets of points linked together by lines which completely enclose the areas of space (Figs)

Location-

Dindori tahsil is selected for the analysis of connectivity matrix. It is located in Nashik District towards north. The geographical area of this tahsil is 13202.50 Sq. km. There are 157 villages. Out of these 20 villages are having more than 3000 population. The roads and vertex of these villages are shown in the map. The latitudinal and longitudinal extension of these villages are as follows.

Sr. No.	Location	Latitude	Longitude
1	Dindori	20.2	73.83
2	KasbeVani	20.33	73.89
3	Mohadi	20.14	73.89
4	Khedgaon	20.23	73.95
5	Janori	20.10	73.88
6	akhamapur	20.27	73.82
7	Kochargaon	20.14	73.65
8	Palkhed	20.18	73.86
9	aterewadi	20.21	73.9
10	Nanashi	20.34	73.62
11	Varkheda	20.24	73.89
12	Chinchkhed	20.16	73.92
13	Bopegaon	20.22	73.93
14	Amnbevani	20.24	73.89
15	Umrle Bk	20.2	73.72
16	Sonjamb	20.25	73.93
17	Vilvandi	20.15	73.62
18	Pimpalnare	20.11	73.78
19	Karanjwan	20.29	73.79
20	Nalwadpada	20.28	73.73

Assessment of link and Node Ratio

There are three groups of ratio measures in network analysis. These are as follows.

1. Alpha Index-

It is also called redundancy index. This consists of the ratio between the observed numbers of fundamental circuits to the maximum number of circuits that may exist in a network. The observed number of fundamental circuits is given by the Cyclomatic number.

$$\text{Alpha } (\alpha) = \text{Actual number of circuits} / \text{maximum number of circuits.}$$
$$= V + G / 2V - 5$$

Where 'e' is the number of edges. 'V' is the number of vertices and 'G' is the number of sub-graphs. The alpha index value will be ranging from 0 to 1.0 where Zero value represents a minimum connected network and value 1 represents a maximum connected network. For the arithmetic convenience the numerical value may also be expressed in percentage.

2. Beta Index

The Beta Index is also called as Cyclomatic number, It is one of the fundamental indices of graph theory. It is the non-ratio measure. It is derived from the equation of $V = E - V + G$ where G represents the sub-graphs in the network where the sub-graph becomes greater than 1.0 the Cyclomatic number is equal to zero. Its most important function is to identify trees and disconnected graphs. Beta index is the simplest form of the three groups of measures.

$$\text{Beta Index } (\beta) = \text{Arcs/Nodes}$$
$$= e/V$$

3. Gamma Index

This is the ratio of the observed number of edges (e) the maximum of edges in a planner graph.

Gamma Index can be measured as follows.

$$\text{Gamma Index } (\gamma) = e / 3(V-2)$$

In any network, the maximum number of direct connections, is strictly a function of the number of nodes present

Spatial Structure of the network-

A relative measure to an analysis of the network configuration is based on the value of alpha and gamma indices Three basic network configurations are spinal, grid and delta.

Table No. 1 Spatial Structure

Sr. No.	Pattern	Alpha	Gamma
1	Spinal	$\alpha=0$	$1/3 \leq \sqrt{\leq} 1/2$
2	Grid	$0 < \alpha < 0.5$	$1/2 \leq \sqrt{\leq} 2/3$
3	Delta	$0.5 < \alpha < 1$	$2/3 \leq \sqrt{\leq} 1.0$

Efficiency of Edges and vertices-

A. Eta Index-

The Eta Index is the ratio of expressing relationship between the transportation network as a whole and its routes as individual elements of the network. In a graph theory measures, the eta index is the ratio of the sum of all edges and all vertices to the observed number of edges of the network. The value of Eta index indicates the nature of accessibility. The low value index indicates high accessibility and vice versa. This indicates accessibility of vertices on the network, as the value decreases over a period of time, the accessibility may increase. It is computed from the formula given below.

$$\text{Eta } (\eta) = \text{Total Route Length} / \text{Total number of edges} \\ = M/e$$

B. Theta Index

Theta Index is a ratio of the network as a whole to its vertices. It is also a measure of length of route per vertex. The important unique property of this index is, it gives information on the length structure and also on the degree of connectivity of the network simultaneously. Theoretically, theta seems to be a more powerful measure than eta and when we compare eta and pie, the theta value does not change its numerical value, although the structure of the network differs. Whereas theta value differs and assigns different numerical values to them. Low value index indicates the maximum accessibility and vice -versa.

$$\text{Theta } (\Theta) = \text{Total Route Length} / \text{Number of Vertices} \\ = M/V$$

C. Pie Index-

Pie is an index measuring the relationship between a transportation network as a whole and specific edges of that network. The pie index usually expresses the circumference of a circle and its diameter. The circumference of a circle is a function of its diameter. The total length

of the network is equal to the circumference of circle and the total length of all edges of the network is compared to the length of diameter of a circle. The visual expression from the graph of pie measure the 'shape' of transportation networks i.e. it is a measure of length per unit of diameter. The low value of pie index indicates the ill connected nature of networks and vice versa. Pie index is calculated by using the following formula.

$$\text{Pie index } (\Pi) = \frac{\text{The total length of the network}}{\text{Length of diameter of the network}} \\ = C/d$$

The Diameter of Networks-

Describing a network by means of its diameter involves the counting of number of arcs in the shortest possible path between the two farthest points on the network. Diameter is a measure of the 'span' of the transportation network system. The diameter is revealed by filling in the shortest path matrix, again to find the longest, i.e. the one with the greatest number of edges.

Density of Networks-

It is the ratio measure of the area to the total edge length. To calculate the overall density per sq. km the following equation is used.

$$\text{Density per sq. Km} = \frac{\text{Total edge length}}{\text{Total area}}$$

Results and Discussion -

The selected graph theory measures are systematically computed by following suitable procedure and steps. There are four steps involved in this process of computation of networks. In the first step, the necessary road network maps with respect to the years 1980 and 2019 have been prepared on the basis of the available base maps by using Turbo Pass Open Software showing various roads and information relating to the tahsil roads. The nodes or vertices (v) and the links between two nodes as the edges (e) are also clearly denoted in respective network maps. At the second step, the road networks of the region have been transformed to the form of topological network by employing the guidelines of the graph theory. In the third step, the selected graph theoretic measures namely alpha, beta, gamma, diameter, eta, theta and pie indices and density of network are computed by

employing the respective formula. Finally, in the fourth step, all the results of above said graph theoretic measures of the years 1980 and 2019 are systematically tabulated.

Table No. 2
The Changing Structural Characteristics of Road Network in Dindori Tahsil

Characteristics	1980	2019
Vertices	17	20
Edges	16	24
Total Length	4.71	637358.06
No .of Circuits	1	6
Cyclomatic Number	0	5
Alpha	0.58	0.74
Beta	0.94	1.2
Gamma	0.35	0.66
Eta	0.29	26556.58
Theta	0.27	31867.90
Pie	0.089	12156.98
Diameter	52.452	52.452
Density	0.000356	48

Transportation Network Analysis

Connectivity Index- Connectivity is the relative degree of connectedness within a transportation network. Places with high connectivity are always considered as important as they are the best connected.

Connectivity Matrix-

Reduce the transportation network to a matrix consisting of ones (1) and zeros (0). Code 1 is used for directly connected link and code 0 is used which are not directly linked.

If two locations connected are directly by a link is coded with zero (0). If two locations are not directly connected is coded with one (1).

Topological Distance-

Topological distance is 1 in the A and B location.

Topological distance is 0 in the A and B location.

Nodes and Vertex Dindori Tahsil 2019

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	0									
2		0								
3			0							
4				0						
5					0					
6						0				
7							0			
8								0		
9									0	
10										0

All other non-directly connected dyads cells coded with a 0 (zero)

First Table (C₁)

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
2	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
3	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
7	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
8	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
11	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
14	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
16	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
17	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
18	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
19	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
20	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0

Power the matrix (multiply the power by itself) to determine all 2 step linkages
Second Table

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
1	8	4	1	0	0	1	1	1	4	0	1	3	2	1	1	0	0	1	1	2
2	4	10	4	0	0	1	1	1	4	0	1	3	2	1	1	0	0	1	1	2
3	1	4	5	3	0	1	1	3	4	0	1	3	2	1	1	0	0	1	1	2
4	0	0	3	5	0	1	1	3	1	0	1	3	2	0	1	0	0	1	1	2
5	0	0	0	0	6	0	1	3	0	2	1	3	2	1	1	0	0	1	1	2
6	1	1	1	1	0	6	1	4	0	4	4	3	2	1	1	0	0	1	1	2
7	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	1	0	1	0	2	2	1	1	0	0	1	1	2
8	1	1	3	3	3	4	1	8	4	1	3	2	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	2
9	4	4	4	1	0	0	0	4	6	0	3	2	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	2
10	0	0	0	0	2	4	1	1	0	4	1	2	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	2
11	1	1	1	1	1	4	0	3	3	1	6	3	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	2
12	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	3	4	2	1	0	0	1	1	1	2
13	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	0	1	1	2	4	1	0	0	1	2	2	1
14	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	6	2	0	2	1	1	1
15	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	2	3	0	0	1	2	2
16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	2	1
17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	2	0	0	2	2	1	1
18	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	2	1	1	2	2	4	1	2
19	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	4	2
20	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	4

Third Table (C₂)

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
1	8	5	2	0	0	2	1	2	4	0	1	3	2	2	2	0	0	2	1	3
2	5	10	4	1	0	2	2	2	4	1	2	3	2	2	1	1	0	2	2	2
3	2	4	5	3	1	1	1	4	5	0	2	4	2	2	1	0	0	1	1	2
4	0	1	3	5	0	1	1	4	2	0	1	4	3	0	1	0	0	1	1	2
5	0	0	1	0	6	0	1	3	0	2	1	3	2	1	1	0	0	1	1	2
6	2	2	1	1	0	6	1	4	0	5	4	3	2	2	1	0	0	1	2	3
7	1	2	1	1	1	1	4	1	0	1	0	3	2	1	2	0	1	2	1	2
8	2	2	4	4	3	4	1	8	5	1	4	3	1	2	1	0	0	1	1	2
9	4	4	5	2	0	0	0	5	6	0	4	3	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	2
10	0	1	0	0	2	5	1	1	0	4	1	2	1	1	1	1	0	1	2	3
11	1	2	2	1	1	4	0	4	4	1	6	3	2	2	0	0	1	0	0	2
12	3	3	4	4	3	3	2	3	3	2	3	4	2	1	0	0	1	1	1	2
13	2	2	2	3	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	4	1	0	1	1	2	2	2
14	2	2	2	0	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	6	2	0	2	1	1	1
15	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	2	3	0	0	2	2	2
16	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	2	1
17	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	2	0	0	2	2	1	1
18	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	0	1	2	1	2	2	2	4	1	2
19	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	0	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	4	2
20	3	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	2	3	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	4

C₁ and C₂Addition

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	Total
1	8	6	3	0	0	3	1	3	4	0	1	3	2	3	3	0	0	3	1	4	48
2	6	10	4	2	0	3	3	3	4	2	3	3	2	3	1	2	0	3	3	2	59
3	3	4	5	3	2	1	1	5	6	0	3	5	2	3	1	0	0	1	1	2	48
4	0	2	3	5	0	1	1	5	3	0	1	5	4	0	1	0	0	1	1	2	35
5	0	0	2	0	6	0	1	3	0	2	1	3	2	1	1	0	0	1	1	2	26
6	3	3	1	1	0	6	1	4	0	6	4	3	2	3	1	0	0	1	3	3	45
7	1	3	1	1	1	1	4	1	0	1	0	3	2	1	3	0	2	3	1	2	31
8	3	3	5	5	3	4	1	8	6	1	5	4	1	3	1	0	0	1	1	2	57
9	4	4	6	3	0	0	0	6	6	0	5	4	2	1	1	0	0	1	1	2	46
10	0	2	0	0	2	6	1	1	0	4	1	2	1	1	1	1	0	1	3	4	31
11	1	3	3	1	1	4	0	5	5	1	6	3	3	3	0	0	1	0	0	2	42
12	3	3	5	5	3	3	2	4	4	2	3	4	2	1	0	0	1	1	1	2	49
13	2	2	2	4	2	2	2	1	2	1	3	2	4	1	0	2	1	2	2	2	39
14	3	3	3	0	1	3	1	3	1	1	3	1	1	6	2	0	2	1	1	1	37
15	3	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	0	0	0	2	3	0	0	3	2	2	25
16	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	2	2	1	11
17	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	1	1	2	0	0	2	2	1	1	15
18	3	3	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	0	1	2	1	3	2	2	4	1	2	34
19	1	3	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	3	0	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	4	2	32
20	4	2	2	2	2	4	2	2	2	3	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	3	4	45

Final Table

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	Total	Rank
1	48	205	152	91	48	127	76	161	155	55	120	131	89	114	80	28	25	98	81	120	2004	3
2	205	59	177	112	54	154	87	192	181	87	145	166	117	129	83	44	31	111	104	136	2374	1
3	152	177	48	126	70	109	62	201	143	67	121	141	98	99	61	27	30	79	73	111	1195	
4	91	112	126	35	53	81	52	145	129	42	101	121	82	55	34	18	17	51	52	75	1472	
5	48	54	70	53	26	60	38	84	59	45	57	73	49	44	30	12	15	36	39	59	951	
6	127	154	109	81	60	45	61	145	107	106	120	118	85	102	57	27	25	65	89	117	1800	5
7	76	87	62	52	38	61	31	70	59	47	49	73	57	54	50	21	28	68	53	68	1104	
8	161	192	201	145	84	145	70	57	206	77	180	192	117	124	65	15	23	74	77	127	2332	2
9	155	181	143	129	59	107	59	206	46	41	148	159	109	20	55	20	20	70	65	111	1903	
10	55	87	67	42	45	106	47	77	41	31	67	71	56	56	40	24	17	47	74	82	1132	
11	120	145	121	101	57	120	49	180	148	67	42	133	88	101	36	15	22	50	59	92	1746	
12	131	166	141	121	73	118	73	192	159	71	133	49	107	92	55	18	22	70	71	113	1975	4
13	89	117	98	82	49	85	57	117	109	56	88	107	39	63	44	27	25	63	62	86	1463	
14	114	129	99	55	44	102	54	124	20	56	101	92	63	37	52	14	27	59	56	79	1377	
15	80	83	61	34	30	57	50	65	55	40	36	55	44	52	25	15	18	54	44	61	959	
16	28	44	27	18	12	27	21	15	20	24	15	18	27	14	15	11	8	25	28	24	421	
17	25	31	30	17	15	25	28	23	20	17	22	22	25	27	18	8	15	32	20	32	452	
18	98	111	79	51	36	65	68	74	70	47	50	70	63	59	54	25	32	34	58	76	1220	
19	81	104	73	52	39	89	53	77	65	74	59	71	62	56	44	28	20	58	32	75	1212	
20	120	136	111	75	59	117	68	127	111	82	92	113	86	79	61	24	32	76	75	45	1689	

Conclusion-

Road network pattern and its structural characteristics are clearly and systematically analyzed with suitable measures like graph theory and matrices. Based on the above analysis the following broad inferences are made

KasbeVani is ranked first in all connectivity and accessibility measures of graph theory. Whileas Sonjamb ranks last (20) in the study area. Total length of Roads increased too much more in 2019 as compare to 1980. Vertices increased by 3 and Edges increased by 8 in 2019 as compare to 1980. Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Eta, Theta and Cyclomatic numbers all are increased.

References-

- 1) Bartelme, Norbert, 2000. Geoinformatik - Modelle, Strukturen, Funktionen. Berlin: Springer-Verlag.
- 2) Bott, Kevin; Ballue, Ronald H., 1986. Research perspectives in vehicle routing and scheduling.. Transport. Res., 20(3), 239-243.

- 3) Foulds, L. and J. Wilson, 1997. A variation of the generalized assignment problem arising in the New Zealand dairy industry.. *Annals of Operations Research*, 69, 105–114.
- 4) Garrison, William L., 1968. Connectivity of the interstate highway system. In: Berry, Brian J.L.; Marble, Duane F., ed. *Spatial analysis: A reader in statistical geography*. Englewood Cliffs: PrenticeHall.
- 5) Gatrell, A.C., 1991. Concepts of space and geographical data. *Geographical Information Systems*, 119-143.
- 6) Gerardo Ubilla-Bravo1 Institut National de Recherche Agronomique (Francia) y Université Paul-Valéry (Francia) Accessibility and Geographical Connectivity in Rural Areas. The Case of Maria Pinto District, Chile
- 7) <http://webspace.ship.edu/pgmarr/TransMeth/Lec%202-Connectivity.pdf>
- 8) Haggett, Peter; Cliff, Andrew D.; Frey, Allan, 1977. *Locational Analysis in Human Geography*. New York: Wiley.
- 9) Jones, Ch., 1997. *Geographical Information Systems and Computer Cartography*. Longman Singapore Publishers (pte) Ltd..
- 10) Sedgewick, Robert, 1998. *Algorithmen*. Bonn: Addison-Wesley.
- 11) Solomon, Marius M., 1987. Algorithms for the Vehicle Routing and Scheduling Problems with Time Window Constraints.. *Operations Research*, 35(2), 254-265.
- 12) Spiekermann, Klaus, 1999. Visualisierung von Eisenbahnreisezeiten – Eininteraktives Computerprogramm. Institut für Raumplanung, Universität Dortmund: Dortmund, Germany, 45. Download: <http://www.raumplanung.uni-dortmund.de/irpud/pro/visual/ber45.pdf>
- 13) Toth, Paolo, 2001. *The Vehicle Routing Problem*. Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics.
- 14) Transport for London (2005). *Tube Maps of London* [online]. London: Mayor of London. Available from: <https://tfl.gov.uk/maps/track/tube> [Accessed 28.04.2016]. Download: [../download/london_tube.pdf](#)